

PRIORITY OF THE PERSON-CENTERED EDUCATIONAL MODEL IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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***Annotation:** In the process of pre-school education, the person-oriented model of education is given priority in the education of a child. The goal of a conscious approach to personality is to develop a personality, not to "change" it under given standards and pressure, but to "accept it as it is." **Approach** aims to create conditions for the development and full manifestation of the personal commitments of the participants of the educational process.*

PERSONAL OBLIGATIONS are the manifestation of certain qualities by an individual that enforces the social order of "being a person".

Determining the teacher's direction between values determines his professional activity. The approach to the individual helps the pedagogue and the child to feel themselves as individuals, to identify and manifest their potential, allows for self-awareness, self-awareness, self-reliance and self-discovery that can be realized by society.

At the preschool age, the child acquires the highest peaks of perception of the individual surface properties of objects, finds solutions to practical and mental tasks in a visual form. But the child is still indifferent to the appearance of objects. This is natural because objects exist for him and they interest the child only as an object of practical and intellectual activity. A child of preschool age acts not on the essence of things, but on their appearance and use. There is a big difference between how things appear to us and what they are. The essence of things is not superficial, it does

not arise behind personal experience, it is not directly perceived. It is discovered through socially organized learning - scientific understanding of the world.

Modified teaching is a radically modified (demonstration-developing) collaborative activity of a child and a pedagogue aimed at the independent education of the pedagogue and the child's personality. universalized system of the child. Radical training involves the following approaches:

Social pedagogical approach. Its content is to implement development that ensures the assimilation of human experience by the child. This approach is aimed at achieving the final result of the educational process - the socialization of the child's personality. Its essence is the radical reformation of the moral and spiritual changes of the society by the child. In such an approach, education plays an educational role.

The epistemological (cognitive activity) approach takes the essence of the teaching process from the cognitive process and modifies (variates) the cognitive activity that has occurred. Education accelerates the individual development of a person, which is subject to social legislation. At the same time, it depends on the individual development of man in the established order, as well as on the general historical development of human consciousness.

Reading brings together the general and individual forms of understanding, brings individual activity closer to the general system of understanding, calls out the differences between the child's personal experiences and concepts that have arisen during reading and teaching.

The essence of epistemological teaching is to implement the process of individualization of the object being taught in the implementation of educational tasks.

Psychological approach. For this approach, human development and acquisition of knowledge consists of bringing to the surface psychological theoretical knowledge.

Taking into account the theory of gradual formation of mental activity (P.Y.A. Galperin, NFTalyzin), teaching moves from the first materialized stage to the second, that is, the stage preserved in the basic external speech activity. After that,

the mental activity goes to the third, higher stage, which is carried out in a completely internal activity. In this approach, the essence of teaching is compared in accordance with the stages of the formation of mental activity. In this approach, teaching is focused on the individual of the learner and implements developmental activities.

Acmeological (from the Greek word meaning high point, rise, good time and study) **approach** reveals the person-centered characteristics of teaching. Its essence lies in the fact that teaching penetrates into the life world of the individual, into the content of the existing life of the pedagogue and the child. Teaching not only harmonizes the thoughts and attitudes of the student and the pedagogue, changes the field of content, but also leads to the emergence and development of a holistic subject of mutual relations. In this, teaching becomes a factor of mutual education, mutual education, mutual cooperation, and mutual creativity.

The application of methodological principles in the educational process has the following educational goals: educational, educational, developmental, practical.

The educational goal of education is to educate the child's needs, to apply the pedagogical point of view (the way of the child to go through "moral stages" through his personal experiences in collective activities led by adults).

The content of the educational goal is that the child develops a system of moral values, an emotional-evaluative attitude to the world.

Educational goal is that the child satisfies his intellectual needs during the educational process and realizes the reality surrounding him.

Educative, educational, developmental, practical goals of education serve as the main factor determining the applied and methodical principles under the condition of choosing appropriate means, methods and methods of teaching. The indicators of the child's development and readiness for school are as follows:

1. Physical preparation (physiological level of the development of the child's content);
2. Psychological preparation (emotional, mental, volitional development level of the child's personality);

3. Social preparation (level of social development of the child in terms of content).

When determining the indicators of the teacher's readiness to implement a person-oriented approach in preschool education, it is necessary to take into account 3 areas: individual, activity-based and reflexive.

Preparation as a person is pedagogical thinking (gnostic, that is, mental abilities - skills to distinguish scientific information, correct application of scientific knowledge in practical activities, competent solution of pedagogical tasks); *setting a pedagogical goal* (organizational skills - the skills of creating optimal conditions for teaching and repetition, choosing the necessary forms of training, the correct distribution of time, providing the educational process with the necessary inventory equipment; organizing one's own work planning and holding any events (mornings, literary evenings, etc.);

pedagogical orientation (communicative skills: the ability to present information in a general form for a certain category of learners, to adjust the methods and methods of providing information depending on the situation, the ability to convince someone, "pedagogue - pedagogue", "pedagogue-parent", "pedagogue-manager", "pedagogue-child" level professional communication; creating a positive psychological microclimate in the children's team, etc.).

Professional training : pedagogic tact (project skills for intellectual work: removing ordinary standards and decision-making methods and looking for new, extraordinary ones; being able to see above this and what is known in itself; coverage; being able to clearly see several different ways of decision-making and choose the most effective one; perception and existence of a problem where all issues are resolved; ideational productivity; individual development of the child in the educational process, innovative designing the curriculum, program, own activities, etc.).

Reflexive training: pedagogical reflection (reflexive skills include 3 types of sensitivity: feeling the object: how real reality resonates with children, to what extent children's interests and needs are manifested in it, "to adapt them to the requirements of the pedagogical system special sensitivity of the pedagogue to the coming"; sense

of the norm and tact is manifested in a special sensitivity to the degree of changes occurring in the child's personality and activity under the influence of various pedagogical influence tools, what kind of feeling in general changes are taking place, whether they are positive or negative, according to which signs it is possible to talk about them; the feeling of commitment is defined by the sensitivity of the pedagogue's personal activity shortcomings, criticality and responsibility for the educational process).

The above indicates that in the implementation of the person-oriented approach, not the individual development of the child and the pedagogue, but the development of the entire subject of the educational process should be implemented.

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